

Reporting relevance, availability, and accessibility of quality information in Earth System Science Data

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Executive Summary

Most Earth System Science (ESS) research projects are data driven and/or produce data sets as main results. Data quality is an essential criterion to evaluate a dataset's fitness for use, describing common characteristics of data from a methodological point of view. In this report we present results of a survey that gathered requirements on data quality information from a data user perspective with the aim to better understand the relevance, availability, and accessibility of data quality information on several levels of details. The survey was online between November 2021 and January 2022.

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Background information

Data management has become an integral part of Earth System Sciences (ESS) research projects, fostering efficient, collaborative, long-term data-driven research. Ensuring access to quality assured data and metadata is of paramount importance in the data life cycle (see Figure 1) as quality information is a fundamental characteristic of data and provides the basis to determine fitness for use. It plays a major role in ESS, because earth observations, e.g. physical or chemical processes, are measured once, and the measured data is reused multiple times. For this reason, a meaningful description of data quality is essential. The survey was developed within the GeoKur project. Within the project, we aim to support the curation and quality assurance of ESS data. The overarching goal is to integrate quality aspects in each phase of the data life cycle, including developing proper metadata schema as well as tools for tracking or visualization of quality information. The developments include concepts, best practices and tools to support research data management for the discovery, reuse, and collaboration across-domain research including heterogeneous data sources. The requirement analysis for the tools includes high efforts in gathering meta information, in particular quality and provenance information, for potential analysis inputs.

Figure 1 Research data lifecycle (<https://www.gfbio.org/training/materials/data-lifecycle/plan>)

Survey on relevance, availability, and needs of quality information in Earth System Science Data

Survey period: November 10, 2021 - January 23, 2022

Survey structure

In the survey, we aim to better understand the relevance, availability, and accessibility of quality information on several levels of details from a data user perspective. The survey was mainly structured around the data quality elements of ISO 19157 - Geographic information - Data quality (ISO 2013) addressing availability and accessibility on several levels of detail. However, provenance information are strongly related to data quality, being key to understand data quality of a product with respect to its development, and are therefore included. The survey was structured in two sections, section 1 on data quality and section 2 on the background of the respondents.

Survey background

Interest in quality information is high and stresses need and relevance of quality information. However, sustainable and user-friendly approaches for data quality tracking, managing and visualizing are often lacking.

In summer 2021 we sent out a similar but longer survey (Egli, Fischer, and Henzen 2021). The response rate was relatively low, apparently due to its complexity and length. However, we received feedback that data quality is an interesting and relevant criterion. We thus substantially revised and simplified the survey. We shared the revised survey broadly within international Earth System Science experts and data users. The survey was sent to project partners and diverse established networks, including universities, Helmholtz Centers and other geodata specialist groups (e.g., ESIP Information Quality Cluster³ or the Association of Geographic Information Laboratories in Europe (AGILE)⁴) with request for further distribution. 39 Participants started filling out the questionnaire. 33 participants filled out section 1 on data quality information and 29 participants filled out the complete questionnaire including section 1 on data quality information and section 2 on background information.

³ https://wiki.esipfed.org/Information_Quality

⁴ <https://agile-online.org/>

Survey results

In this chapter, we provide an overview of the questions and answers, structured along the original survey.

Section 1: Data quality

Q1 - Which data quality information is relevant for you to evaluate a dataset's fitness for use? (free text answer)

Figure 2 Data quality information mentioned as being relevant (total number of respondents $n = 33$)

Q2 - Is provenance (or lineage) information relevant for you to evaluate a dataset's fitness for use? (selection)

Figure 3 Relevance of provenance information to evaluate a dataset's fitness for use (total number of respondents n = 33)

Q3 - How would you rate the availability of the mentioned data quality and provenance information in general? & Q4 - How would you rate the accessibility of the mentioned data quality and provenance information in general? (both scale: 1 = Low; 5 = High)

Table 1 Mean availability and accessibility of data quality (DQI) and provenance information (0 = low, 5 = high). 'Times mentioned (a)' indicates the number of times the respective quality information or provenance has been mentioned as being relevant (Question Q1). (total number of respondents n = 29)

DQI	Times mentioned (a)	Mean availability	Mean accessibility
19157	1	2.00	2.00
accuracy and precision	1	3.00	2.00
availability of metadata	2	4.00	4.00
completeness	15	3.31	3.23
continuity of a time series	1	1.00	4.00
file type (e.g. shp, geotiff)	1	4.00	1.00
georeferenced sequence data	1	2.00	3.00
identified errors	3	2.33	2.33
instrumental bias	2	4.00	3.50
life history traits	1	3.00	3.00
logical consistency	8	3.00	2.86
positional accuracy	12	3.55	3.18
provenance	26	2.64	2.68
quality of the method behind the data	1	4.00	4.00
reliability	2	5.00	5.00
reputation of data developer	1	5.00	5.00
resolution (positional accuracy)	1	5.00	5.00
scale	1	NA	NA
semantic accuracy	1	4.00	1.00
semantic definition	1	3.00	2.00
source	2	4.00	4.00
spatial extent	3	5.00	3.33
spatial resolution	5	4.25	3.50
temporal coverage	8	2.86	3.29
temporal quality	5	3.25	3.25

DQI	Times mentioned (a)	Mean availability	Mean accessibility
temporal resolution	2	4.50	4.00
thematic accuracy	15	3.46	3.31
uncertainty	1	3.00	3.00
usability	5	3.60	3.40

Q5 - If data quality and provenance information is available, where do you typically obtain it from? (multiple choice)

Figure 4 Current source of data quality and provenance information (total number of respondents n = 31)

Q6 - Where would you like to get data quality and provenance information from? (multiple choice)

Figure 5 Preferred source of data quality and provenance information (total number of respondents n = 31)

Q7 - Which level of detail do you prefer for the mentioned data quality information? (multiple choice matrix)

Table 2 Preferred level of detail of data quality information (DQI). 'Times mentioned (a)' indicates the number of respondents which named the respective quality information as being relevant (Question Q1). Values of 'Quality flag', 'Categories', 'Continuous values' and 'Differentiated for region / topic / period' indicate the number of respondents which prefer the respective level of detail. (total number of respondents n = 24)

DQI	Times mentioned (a)	Quality flag	Categories	Continuous values	Differentiated for region / topic / period
19157	1	1	1	0	0
accuracy and precision	1	0	0	1	0
availability of metadata	2	0	0	0	0
completeness	15	4	4	3	3
continuity of a time series	1	0	1	0	0
file type (e.g. shp, geotiff)	1	0	1	0	0
georeferenced sequence data	1	0	0	0	0
identified errors	3	0	1	0	2
instrumental bias	2	1	1	0	0
life history traits	1	0	0	0	1
logical consistency	8	2	3	0	2
positional accuracy	12	2	3	4	6
quality of the method behind the data	1	0	0	0	1
reliability	2	1	2	0	0
reputation of data developer	1	0	0	0	0
resolution (positional accuracy)	1	1	1	0	0
scale	1	0	0	0	0
semantic accuracy	1	0	1	0	0
semantic definition	1	0	0	0	1
source	2	0	0	0	1
spatial extent	3	0	0	2	1

DQI	Times mentioned (a)	Quality flag	Categories	Continuous values	Differentiated for region / topic / period
spatial resolution	5	0	0	4	1
temporal coverage	8	1	1	2	5
temporal quality	5	1	0	3	1
temporal resolution	2	0	1	1	1
thematic accuracy	15	0	7	2	6
uncertainty	1	0	0	1	0
usability	5	1	1	0	3

Q8 - What type of presentation do you prefer for data quality information? (multiple choice)

Figure 6 Preferred type of presentation for data quality information (total number of respondents n = 31)

Q9 - For a given application, how do you evaluate the fitness for use of input datasets? (multiple choice)

Figure 7 Approach of fitness-for-use evaluation of input datasets (total number of respondents $n = 29$)

Q10 - What other aspects do you consider to evaluate the fitness for use of input datasets? (multiple choice)

Figure 8 Considered aspects of fitness-for-use evaluation of input datasets (total number of respondents n = 30)

Q11 - How useful are concepts that link data quality and provenance information to evaluate the fitness for use of input datasets? (multiple choice)

Figure 9 Usefulness of concepts that link data quality and provenance information for fitness-for-use evaluation of input datasets (total number of respondents n = 29)

Section 2: Background

B1 - Which of the following options best describes your profession? (multiple choice)

Figure 10 Profession (total number of respondents n = 29)

B2 - Which is your main target audience? (multiple choice)

Figure 11 Main target audience (total number of respondents n = 29)

B3 - In which country is your organization based? (suggesting text input)

Figure 12 Country of organization (total number of respondents n = 29)

B4 - How often do you work with geodata? (selection)

Figure 13 Frequency of geodata use (total number of respondents n = 29)

B5 - What are your main research disciplines/domains (free text answer)

Table 3 Main research disciplines or domains (total number of respondents n = 29)

Discipline 1	Discipline 2	Discipline 3
Ecology		
soil physics, geohydrology		
soil system science, agroecology		
climate research, ecosystem research		
climate research		
geoinformatics		
Agroecology		
biogeography	nature conservation	animal ecology
ecology	biogeography	
agroecology	hydrology	
hydrology (including some climate research)		
Biogeography	Molecular phylogenetics	Genetic diversity
Land systems science	Land use/land cover change	
	disease ecology	
Environement/ecosystem services	geoinformatics	remote sensing
CRYOSPHERE		
agricultural economics, sustainability research		
urban geography	uhi	inequality exposure
Public Health		
Spatial planning	Climate change	Regional development
landscape ecology	geography	
hydrology		
geoinformatics	geography	remote sensing
geoinformation science	environmental science	spatial planning

Discipline 1	Discipline 2	Discipline 3
geoinformatics	land-use and land-cover	VGI user assessment
biogeography	nature conservation	
aquatic ecology		

B6 - Which variables are mainly described by the geodata you work with? (free text answer)

Table 4 Variables mainly described by the geodata used (total number of respondents n = 29)

Variable 1	Variable 2	Variable 3	Variable 4	Variable 5	Variable 6	Variable 7
species distribution	climate	soil				
precipitation	potential evapotranspiration	soil hydraulic properties	aquifer properties		soil water content, soil water matric potential	
soil water content, soil tension, soil temperature, soil water budget						
carbon and water fluxes, climatological variables						
precipitation	land cover					
Location-related variables						
Land use and land cover	Climate	Biodiversity	Ecosystem services	Soil parameters		
species occurrence	land cover and land use	climate (temperature, precipitation)	topography			
species composition (and then richness is just one of the derived metrics)	temperature (several aspects of)	temperature (precipitation aspects of)	soil moisture (several aspects of)	land cover	land use/intensity (if only I could get reliable large extent, high resolution data...)	species traits (placed into space using species identity from compositional data)
land cover	soils & soil properties	land management	water bodies			
climate data	hydrologic data incl. digital elevation model	land cover				
DNA sequence data	species distribution maps	life history trait data	museum data			

Variable 1	Variable 2	Variable 3	Variable 4	Variable 5	Variable 6	Variable 7
Land cover	Climate variables (precipitation, temperature, PET...)	Soil characteristics (clay, sand content, SOC, pH..)				
land cover, human population and other socioeconomic indicators						
land cover/land use	spectral reflectance	elevation				
spatial extent of land and sea ice, snow cover	land surface elevation	soil moisture				
land cover	water use	crop yields and production				
land use	demographics	air pollution				
Socio Economic						
many different variables; currently soil, land cover, climate, demography, nature protection						
land cover	land use					
climate, surface discharge, groundwater levels, chemical parameters,						
land cover	administrative units					
land-cover	species imagery	collection of all				
Land cover	Land use	Habitat connectivity	Biodiversity	Ecosystem integrity		
land cover	elevation	river network				

References

- Egli, L., J. Fischer, and C. Henzen. 2021. Reporting relevance, availability, and needs of quality information in Earth System Science Data. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5562326.
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